

CALL in Promoting EFL Learner Autonomy at the Tertiary Level in Bangladesh

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Abstract: *This research article intends to examine how far Computer Assisted Language Learning promotes the autonomous EFL learning and how this can be maximized, overcoming the limitations it has in practical fields. An autonomous learner uses his personal ways of learning according to his need and knowledge on the subject. At the same time he/she sets his own target and evaluates the improvement. CALL can facilitate and give support in all these aspects. So, in general sense we do assume that CALL should promote autonomous EFL learning. But in the context of Bangladesh we need to find out what are strengths and limitations of CALL activities in facilitating EFL learner autonomy. In this paper the researcher has given a general idea of current practices of CALL activities on autonomous language learning. And then he tried to analyze the prevailing limitations of CALL activities to finalize the guidelines later to maximize benefits of EFL autonomous learners. Thereafter he has conducted a questionnaire survey to analyze the present scenario of CALL activities to mould a proper guideline to get the best result for EFL autonomous learners of Bangladesh in the tertiary level.*

Keywords: *Computer-assisted language learning, learner autonomy, tertiary level, English as a foreign language*

Introduction

The main concern of today's language teachers is how to empower their students to become autonomous. With the availability of computer technology, CALL has become a powerful tool in teaching students a foreign language. Computer technology is advancing very fast with new dimensions and innovations. It has opened immense possibilities for the students who want to be autonomous learners. If we analyze the recent researches, we do find that learners are really getting benefits from CALL programs and they are improving a lot regarding their level of proficiency in the target language. The outcome of CALL program is so encouraging for the learners of Bangladesh. In this research, CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning) refers to every kind of use of computer technology. This means searching for online resources, communication through computers, e-mailing, chatting, discussions and any other activities related to computer. Basically CALL is a tool that can be used in learning a foreign language. On the other hand, in the autonomous learning, learners are accountable and do all the works by themselves to learn the language. CALL thus gives opportunities for the learners to become autonomous.

Autonomous learning has become very effective at present time because learners are deeply involved in the learning process. They set their target, make plans for achieving the goal. They themselves monitor their progress and evaluate the results. Autonomous learners are more focused, so better learning is possible. Learners take all the responsibilities of their own learning (Holec, 1981; Little, 1991; Dam, 1995). Every learner has their own potentialities and they need to explore it. In autonomous learning, learners take all the actions for their learning. They make their own decisions. They feel the ownership. They are more committed to their actions. This gives better results, better performances, and better fluency in the target language. So scopes should be given to learners to develop their skills by themselves. They should know how to manage their own learning environment and use the appropriate materials, when teacher is not with them, outside the classroom. They should be motivated to take their own learning responsibilities. They need to learn how to control their own learning environment and supervise their development. They ought to be familiar with their own learning method and strategies and decide their materials and tasks.

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And most importantly they should be willing to take risks (Dam, 1995. Wenden, 1998). In this regard CALL programs can prove to be a great tool for them.

Basically, CALL and Autonomous EFL learning are closely related. CALL is very much influential and motivating tool. CALL gives great potentiality to the autonomous learners. It is very much encouraging that currently Bangladesh is also experiencing a technological 'boom' and learners are very much eager to be a part of it. That is why the impact and influence of CALL in fostering EFL autonomous learning in Bangladesh at the tertiary level is undeniable. In recent years CALL is already playing significant task in language learning distinctively in foreign language learning all over the world. CALL is an effectual tool in learning all the essential parts of language learning. CALL activities can be used in all the four skills, listening, speaking, reading and writing. Learners can practice again and again through computers. There is no time limitation. Even computer can check the errors and learners can get feedback using different software and thus improve autonomously. There are so many websites and software that help to improve learners' analytic power and critical thinking ability. Online dictionaries and grammar-checks come to a great use to the autonomous learners. There is software that helps learners to compose language. This kind of tools also gives opportunities to check references, citations and prevent plagiarism' (Milton, 1997). Thus CALL helps students to accurate their answers. Students can thus learn from their mistakes.

Computer is such a tool that has huge storage, so students can store a huge number of learning materials. It also can create an interesting atmosphere for learner, where students feel encouraged to study more. Learning to use the computer assisted technology, as a prodigy and innovative tool, provides a strong motivation for EFL learners to become autonomous learners. In true sense CALL has made an evolution in language learning approaches. If this tool can be used in proper way students can be hugely benefited from this. CALL offers enormous opportunities and advantages for autonomous learners and so the possibilities are also endless. Thus CALL, by its very nature, provides unlimited prospect for learners to become more focused, skilled and autonomous in the target language. CALL creates possibility for self-learning. CALL maximizes learning opportunities for the learners. It enhances the motivation level of the learners and there are no time limitations. Students can do practices as many times as they want. They can see their errors and correct them and thus improve. They can access authentic materials as many as they want and use them repeatedly. This increases their efficiency level. They get fun in using variety of materials. This motivates them to learn more. CALL is able to provide real-life materials and exercises. This does sharpen students' skills better. CALL saves time. Students can get access to any material from any source with just a click on the mouse. Considering the above mentioned discussion it can be said that CALL "do promote autonomous learning by engaging, stimulating, and creating opportunities for learners to be focused and taking responsibilities of their own learning. (Rephrased, Little, 1996). CALL activities like exchange of e-mails stimulates meta-cognitive consciousness: students can reproduce on their own effort. They can themselves understand their mistakes sentence structure, terminology, syntax, language and metaphorical strategies. They become expert in using encyclopedia or dictionary. They need not to waste much time and can smoothly study (Rephrased, Shield, Weininger and Davies, 1999). From a lot of researches done by researchers mentioned top portions of this section gives prove that in promoting EFL learner autonomy CALL had played a significant role outside Bangladesh. It is also mentionable that CALL can do the same in tertiary level in Bangladesh as CALL programs are emerging very fast in this country. We can see that in some of our joint web-page formation ventures, for example, Toyoda (2001) mentions that students 'could plan their strategies autonomously and 'were capable to go on with their works devoid of their teachers' direct directions...'

Indeed CALL has created new opportunities for both English teachers and learners in Bangladesh. Computer and Internet gives numerous opportunity to get access to huge diversity of reliable resources connecting to all compasses of life at nearly no price. CALL activities are capable to

make familiar with a great number of new vocabularies as well as their uses in language in proper way to the students. Call gives great advantage to the learners by giving them their own pace. It also can ensure students own style of learning. Students can learn at their planned strategies. By using CALL learners can keep on practicing exercises and thus attain desired expertise in the desired language. So in a country like Bangladesh, where English is a foreign language computer is the invaluable source of information for learners to become autonomous EFL learners and explore the whole world just by clicking the mouse. So undoubtedly CALL can open up immense possibility for learners, properly guided by teachers, to become autonomous as well as skilled in English language in Bangladesh at university level.

Problem Statement

This is very much convincing that CALL can be the most effective and interesting tool for the autonomous learner to learn a foreign language in the world but in the context of Bangladesh how it affects our EFL learners' autonomy it is still to be identified. Despite the fact that the possibilities are endless in Bangladesh, CALL activities are very nominal and not to the expected level at university level and our learners are not benefited to the maximum level as it should be. So, the strengths and limitations of CALL programs in Bangladesh need to be identified to maximize the use of CALL to make our learners more skilled in English. That is why the research intended to answer the question of how a CALL task can be made successful in promoting learner's autonomy in the context of Bangladesh taking the tertiary level under its consideration. In this research the researcher will inspect the limitations on the use of CALL in Bangladesh. The researcher will try to how these limitations can be minimized, so that learners can get the best output from this. This research aims to unravel the problems and limitations offering a complete guideline for ensuring the maximum benefit from it.

Research Questions

The research questions are as follows:

- 1] How far does CALL promote EFL learner-autonomy at the tertiary level in Bangladesh?
- 2] What are the strengths and limitations of CALL programs in Bangladesh?
- 3] How can CALL task be made successful in promoting EFL learner autonomy at the tertiary level in Bangladesh?

Research Strategy and Methodology

Subjects

The researcher has taken responses from thirty eight English teachers (who are teaching at tertiary level) and two hundred university students arbitrarily nominated from seven universities-Daffodil International University, Eastern University, University of Development Alternative, Dhaka University, Stamford University, State University of Bangladesh and Jahangirnagar University. All the teachers were facilitating EFL learners and all the students were EFL learners.

Tools

To test the 'Research Questions' and to find out the solutions, a quantitative method was followed. This study used two questionnaires for the research. One was designed for the teachers and the other was to record the responses of students. There were eight questions in each questionnaire. Both the questionnaires had almost the same questions. This helped the researcher to compare the views of the both groups.

Data Analysis

To examine the effect of CALL program on EFL autonomous learners at tertiary level the researcher has critically analyzed the data collected from teachers and students. The researcher

physically moved to collect the responses from the teachers. He provided the questionnaire to them, explained all the items of the questionnaire in detail and asked them to fill it up. On the other hand to collect data from the students he took help of the teachers who were teaching them English. He provided detail instruction before taking the responses of the students, so that no confusion arises. All the data were then manually scored.

Questionnaire for Teachers

There were eight questions in teachers' questionnaire. The questions were composed to know the opinion of teachers' on diverse aspects of CALL and EFL learner autonomy. The responses of the thirty eight English teachers were analyzed item-wise in the following manner:

The opening statement for the teachers was related to the outcome of autonomous learning on the success of language learners.

Teachers' Table: 1

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy has a positive effect on the success of a language learner.	12	18	6	2	0
Percentage-wise	32%	47%	16%	5%	0%

N=38

The above Teachers' Table: 1 indicates that $(32\%+47\%)=79\%$ of the teachers more or less approved that autonomous learning gives positive outcome to the learner of language though 16% were not sure about it and 5% disagreed to this issue. This finding indicates that maximum number of the teachers found autonomous learning effective for language learners. It also, shows that teachers have positive attitude towards learners' autonomy as it "empowers the learning of learners and therefore it is one of the main points of language-skill development to encourage the autonomy in learning process" (Toyoda, 2001).

The second statement for the teachers was related to the focus point of autonomous learners in their learning.

Teachers' Table: 2

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy allows learners becoming more focused in language learning.	12	22	2	2	0
Percentage-wise	32%	58%	5%	5%	0%

N=38

The Teachers' Table:2 indicates that 32% of the teachers strongly agreed and 58% agreed in autonomous learning students become further focused in their learning process whereas 5% was not sure about it and only 5% disagreed. So, Teacher Table: 2 clearly reveals that a great majority of the learners are more integrated into language learning when they are more autonomous.

The third statement for the teachers was framed to know whether learners can learn better when they do choose their learning materials by their own choice or not.

Teachers' Table: 3

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy is promoted when learners can choose their own learning materials and the way of learning.	6	22	8	2	0
Percentage-wise	15%	58%	21%	5%	0%

N=38

It is noticeable from Teachers' Table: 3 that a large number of (15%+58%)=73% teachers agreed and strongly agreed to this opinion whereas 21% were not sure about it and only 5% disagreed. This statistics noticeably reveal that maximum teachers were in favor of giving learners opportunities to choose their way of learning and materials to help them becoming autonomous.

The fourth issue in the Teachers' questionnaire was about CALL activities, whether it promotes autonomous learning or not.

Teachers' Table: 4

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy is promoted by independent CALL activities.	4	20	14	0	0
Percentage-wise	10%	53%	37%	0%	0%

N=38

The Teachers' Table: 4 demonstrates that 10% teachers strongly agreed and 53% agreed that independent work in CALL activities promotes learner autonomy though 37% were not sure about its effect. This indicates that when learners take their own decisions, plan their own strategies then learners' autonomy is better promoted.

The fifth concern for the teachers was whether 'Learner autonomy is enhanced through regular opportunities in completing tasks alone with computers' or not.

Teachers' Table: 5

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy is enhanced through regular opportunities in completing tasks alone with computers.	2	26	8	2	0
Percentage-wise	5%	68%	21%	5%	0%

N=38

Teachers' Table: 5 unfolds that at least 73% teachers are more or less agreed that learner autonomy is enhanced through regular opportunities in completing tasks alone with computers. 21% were not confident about this. This result sums up that maximum teachers are with the opinion that when

learners get regular opportunities to use computers they become more autonomous. So learners need to be motivated, so that they can become self independent to learn better from the computer software which is premeditated for language learning. This idea is supported by Milton, J. (1997), who states 'with CALL, individual learners gets chances to workout of their personal comfort areas and can become more productive. This positively enhances students' language learning.

The sixth question in the Teachers' questionnaire was 'Learners Autonomy should be fully independent learning'.

Teachers' Table: 6

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
'Learners Autonomy should be fully independent learning'.	2	12	2	20	2
Percentage-wise	5%	32%	5%	53%	5%

N=38

If we analyze the responses of Teachers' Table:6, we find that a moderate number of 37% teachers were more or less agreed in the issue that autonomous learning means no presence of teacher while a big number of 58% teachers disagreed or strongly disagreed with this issue. So, no reduction of Teachers' part was suggested, rather it can be an alter of dependability. The teachers can play a role as a facilitator or guide or counselor and so forth. Thus they canrender individual help towards autonomous learning.

The next question for teachers was intended to know whether learner autonomy can be promoted without the assistance of teachers.

Teachers' Table: 7

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
'Autonomous learners cannot improve devoid of the guidance from teachers.'	10	10	10	8	0
Percentage-wise	26%	26%	26%	21%	0%

N=38

Teachers' Table:7 shows that 52% teachers were somewhat agreed with the statement that learner autonomy only can develop when teachers' proper guidance is present, though 26% were not sure about this and another 21% disagreed to this issue. This statistics indicates that teachers has great role to play in promoting learning autonomy. If teachers are resourceful and guides students properly, it will make the task easy for learners to follow the right materials to learn better. Students will understand better what their roles in autonomous learning are and how CALL can assist them in this regard.

The eighth issue in the Teachers' Questionnaire was related to the limitations of CALL activities.

The researcher wanted to know what are the prevailing problems of CALL activities in Bangladesh that are restricting the improvement of learners' autonomy.

Teachers' Table: 8

Limitations of CALL activities in promoting learner autonomy at the tertiary level in Bangladesh. Lack of-		Number	Percentage-wise
A]	Computers	14	37%
B]	Internet support	12	32%
C]	Technical knowledge	34	89%
D]	Proper guidance	30	79%
E]	Motivation	14	37%
F]	Authentic Materials	14	37%

The above Teachers' Table:8 reveals that the lack of 'Technical knowledge' and 'Proper guidance' are the main limitations of CALL activities in promoting EFL learner autonomy as they got the maximum number of 89% and 79% teachers' vote. Other 37% ticked for 'Lack of computers', 32% for 'Lack of Internet support', and 37% for 'Lack of motivation and 'Authentic materials' as the limitations. This finding discloses that lack of technical knowledge and the lack of proper guidance hampered the autonomous learning of EFL learners in Bangladesh specially at tertiary level. the most. Besides, the lack of motivation, the lack of computer support and authentic materials are also responsible, to some extent, for restricting the EFL autonomous learning.

Questionnaire for Students

There were eight questions in the questionnaire of students. The questions were formed to collect the responses of students related to the different issues of CALL and learner autonomy. The answers of 200 students are analyzed in the below sections:

The first item for Students' questionnaire was 'Learner autonomy has positive effect on EFL learning'.

Students' Table: 1

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy has positive effect on EFL learning'.	102	64	30	2	2
Percentage-wise	51%	32%	15%	1%	1%

N=200

Students' Table: 1 shows that a great number of 83% students at least agreed that autonomous learning has a positive effect on their EFL learning along with that only 15% were not sure about its effect. But interestingly only 1% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed to this proposition. So it is clear that if learners are empowered in their language learning it definitely makes them proficient, which supports the argument of Richards and Rogers (2002).

The next question for students was 'Learner autonomy allows learners to be more focused in language learning'.

Students' Table: 2

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy allows learners to be more focused in language learning.	112	46	18	10	14
Percentage-wise	56%	23%	9%	5%	7%

N=200

The finding of Students' Table: 2 is closely correlated to the involvement of autonomous learners into their language learning. A great majority of the students (56%+23%) =79% felt that learners are more focused in their language learning when they are autonomous. This result suggests that if the learners are autonomous they become more involved in the target language and learning process which makes them more proficient in the target language.

The third issue of the Students' questionnaire was composed to know whether autonomous learning is promoted when learners take the responsibility to decide their learning materials and style of learning or not.

Students' Table: 3

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy is promoted when learners can choose their own learning materials and way of learning.	22	46	34	74	24
Percentage-wise	11%	23%	17%	37%	12%

N=200

The statistics in the Students' Table:3 shows a mixed result. Whereas (11%+23%)=34% agreed or strongly agreed to this proposal, (17%+37%)=49% disagreed or strongly disagreed to this and 17% were found unsure about it. Compared to the teachers' opinion in this regard it is somewhat a bit different from the students' opinion. So the students are not that much confident about their way of learning and choosing the proper materials for themselves. In this issue the teachers can guide them well and help them choose the right material for them.

The fourth point for the students was to understand what is the effect of CALL programs in developing learners' autonomy.

Students' Table: 4

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy is promoted by independent CALL activities'.	96	88	12	2	0
Percentage-wise	48%	44%	6%	1%	0%

N=200

Students' Table: 4 shows that a huge percentage of students (48%+44%) =92% felt that CALL activities do develop learner autonomy. It also makes learning effective and interesting. Only 1% disagreed with this hypothesis. The result proves that CALL has positive effect on EFL

autonomous learning. According to Philip, M. (1986);CALL gives great self-access facility to **learning.** CALL gives learners freedom of choice which promotes autonomy in learning.

The 5th statement for students was designed to know whether learners become more autonomous while studying alone with CALL facilities or not.

Students' Table: 5

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Learner autonomy is enhanced through regular opportunities in completing tasks alone with computers	82	90	20	8	2
Percentage-wise	41%	45%	10%	4%	1%

N=200

As per the statistics in Students' Table: 5, a good number of students (41%+45%) =86% more or less agreed with the statement, yet 10% could not decide it. In fact CALL offers aimmensediversity of exercises for individual learners to practice language skills. All kinds of study material and exercises are available for autonomous learners in CALL programs.

The sixth proposition of the students' questionnaire was designed as 'Learners Autonomy should be fully independent learning'.

Students' Table: 6

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
'Learners Autonomy should be fully independent learning'.	14	14	22	72	80
Percentage-wise	7%	7%	11%	36%	40%

N=200

As exhibited in Students' Table: 6, only 14% students were more or less agreed with this statement while a maximum of 76% did not agreed to this. It indicates that autonomous learners need the **help** of teachers to guide them becoming independent. The main focus of the teachers should be **motivation** and work on developing the self esteem of learners, so that they can achieve their **desired** autonomy taking CALL activities under the consideration.

The 7th issue was set as 'Autonomous learners cannot improve devoid of the guidance from teachers.'

Students' Table: 7

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
'Autonomous learners cannot improve devoid of the guidance from teachers.'	88	84	8	12	8
Percentage-wise	44%	42%	4%	6%	4%

N=200

Students' Table: 7 shows that 44% students strongly agreed and 42% at least agreed with the notion that without the **correct** guidance of teacher autonomous students cannot achieve their desired result. Only 4% were not sure about it. This indicates that teachers' guidelines are very much

important and helpful for the learners to become autonomous in their language learning. This is supported by Sheer in (1997) who thinks that teachers should prepare and support the students to achieve greater autonomy.

The number eight item of the students' questionnaire was intended to determine the limitations of CALL related EFL learner autonomy.

Students' Table: 8

Limitations of CALL activities in promoting learner autonomy at the tertiary level in Bangladesh. Lack of-		Number	Percentage-wise
A]	Computers	64	32%
B]	Internet support	112	56%
C]	Technical knowledge	144	72%
D]	Proper guidance	104	52%
E]	Motivation	34	17%
F]	Authentic Materials	50	25%

Resembling the findings of the teachers', Students' Table:8, also discover that the lack of technical knowledge (72%), lack of internet support (56%) and lack of proper guidance (52%) are indicated as the main limitations of CALL activities. Again, shortage of computers (32%) and lack of authentic materials (25%) also reduce the facilities of autonomous learners. Interestingly, they did not feel the lack of motivation in themselves that much as the researcher expected. Only (17%) ticked for that. So our learners are motivated enough, only the other factors are hampering their enhancement of autonomous EFL learning. So these limitations should be minimized for better effective autonomous EFL learning.

Findings

On the basis of the above data analysis we can say that to become proficient in a foreign language autonomous learning plays a very vital role. And CALL does promote autonomous learning. CALL can provide all the necessary facilities for an autonomous learner. The study also finds that CALL generates opportunities for learners to become self-reliant. The above analysis also shows that if proper guidance is given CALL can enhance learner autonomy and language learners can learn better. CALL provides autonomous learners the opportunity to decide their own learning materials. Learners can also choose their own learning strategies and become independent learners. But the lack of computers, internet support, technical knowledge, proper guidelines, motivation and authentic materials can limit the success of CALL dependent EFL autonomous learning. At the same time, devoid of any assistance from the teachers, learners cannot achieve their desired results. That is why the best encouragement should be given by their teachers to become autonomous with CALL activities. Teachers should prepare them, guide them, and motivate them to be self-reliant in their language learning process. T the same time we should remember that the level of expertise of student in using technology or computer are not the same. So, they should be given proper training also in this regard. So, CALL along with learners' autonomy is clearly a good tool to facilitate the development of EFL learners in Bangladesh at the tertiary level. This research study claims that the best way to make EFL learners autonomy successful learners need:1) frequent access to computers 2) authenticresources3) expertise in computer technology4) proper guidance from teachers and5) sufficient motivation for learners.

Recommendations

The findings of the data analysis suggest that EFL learner autonomy is highly promoted with CALL activities. To bring out the best and to promote learner autonomy, CALL activities need to be ensured. For this purpose following issues need to be taken into consideration:

- 1] Learners need to be provided with sufficient computer facilities along with high speed internet connection. For financial constraints it may not be possible for all the learners to be provided with individual computers. So the institutions can set up computer labs along with internet connections where learner can get full access at their time of need.
- 2] Along with the technological facilities, technical knowledge is also required. So institutions will arrange training programs for the learners time to time. The learners can themselves also receive some training on it.
- 3] All CALL activities and all internet sites are not equally helpful for promoting learners autonomy. So, instruction on CALL activities and proper guidelines for selecting web-sites should be provided to bring out the best from it.
- 4] Proper and authentic materials are to be selected for the autonomous learners, otherwise things can go wrong.
- 5] Most importantly, motivation is a factor that needs to be ensured to achieve learner autonomy in an effective way.

Conclusion

Foreign language learning, by its nature requires motivation, cultural knowledge, social context and the higher order thinking skills of synthesis and CALL fulfills all these requirements. In a word, CALL promotes EFL learner autonomy in the context of Bangladesh in tertiary level. But learners need to make best use of the tool. In the same process, the teachers also need to take part in developing students' sense of autonomy along with suggesting the right materials for them. The research shows that there are some constraints like the lack of computers and internet connections, lack of proper guidelines and motivations and materials which can limit the promotion of EFL autonomous learning at the tertiary level in Bangladesh. But if we can minimize these limitations, our EFL learners can achieve an excellent autonomous environment that can lead them to attain a higher level of language proficiency. So, the language learners, who have the prime objective to develop autonomy in learning, need to make the best effectual utilization of CALL programs. CALL makes autonomous learning interesting, persuasive. It makes learners self dependant and fully focused to the target language Thus we can declare that CALL can significantly promote EFL learners' autonomy in Bangladesh at the tertiary level, when we can make the best apply of it. Thus, it can be concluded in promoting EFL learners autonomy in Bangladesh at the tertiary level, CALL plays definitely a positive role.

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